

New Antimicrobial Agents : Preparation of Substituted Pyrazoles and Isoxazoles

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Manuscript received 20 January 1981, revised 30 May 1981, accepted 14 August 1981

Different substituted benzene diazonium chlorides were coupled with some reactive methylene compounds and then condensed with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride to obtain substituted pyrazoles and isoxazoles. Some of them have been screened for their antibacterial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory activity.

A good deal of importance is being given to pyrazoles and isoxazoles and their derivatives due to their wide use in medicinal chemistry¹⁻⁵. Some of the pyrazoles have also been found to possess anticancer property⁶. Keeping this in view, substituted benzenediazonium chlorides have been coupled with acetyl acetone, benzoyl acetone and *p*-methyl benzoyl acetone. The resulting products (I) were then refluxed with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively to give some substituted pyrazoles(II) and isoxazoles(III). Two isomeric pyrazoles(II) and isoxazoles(III) could, however, be expected from an unsymmetrical diketone, but only one isomer was obtained. Similar results were obtained by earlier workers⁷⁻⁹ in the reaction of benzoyl acetone with different amines, who reported the formation of only one isomer. Similarly, reaction of *o*-benzoyl 3-nitroacetophenone (3-nitrobenzoyl-benzoyl methane)⁹ with phenylhydrazine gave only 1-phenyl-3-(3'-nitrophenyl)-5-phenyl pyrazole. The purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were tested by tlc and elemental analysis.

The reaction in general may be represented as follow :

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

(i) *4*-Bromo-2-methyl-benzeneazo acetyl acetone(I) : 4-Bromo-2-methyl aniline (1.86 g, 1 mol)

was diazotised in the usual manner and treated with a well cooled mixture of acetyl acetone (1.5 g, 1.5 mol) in ethanol (2.5 ml) and sodium acetate (10 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of water. A yellow precipitate of 4-bromo-2-methyl benzeneazo acetyl acetone started separating out immediately and was collected after 6 hrs. This was recrystallised from ethanol.

(ii) *1*-Phenyl-3, 5-dimethyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl benzeneazo) pyrazole : A mixture of I (2.97 g, 1 mol) dissolved in ethanol and phenylhydrazine (1.08 g, 1 mol) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 4 hrs on water bath. 1-Phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl-benzeneazo)-pyrazole, obtained as orange crystals on cooling, was recrystallised from ethanol.

(iii) *3,5*-Dimethyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl-benzeneazo)-isoxazole : A mixture of I (3.70 g, 1.25 mol) in excess of ethanol, aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g, 1.25 mol) and sodium acetate (5 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was refluxed for 4 hrs on water bath. 3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl-benzeneazo)-isoxazole, obtained as yellow crystals on cooling, was recrystallised from ethanol.

All the other compounds were prepared by the above procedure. In some cases, however, products (I) on treatment with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave resinous mass from which the desired products (II) and (III) could not be isolated. The melting points and yields of all the compounds are given in Table 1.

Antibacterial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory activity : Some of the pyrazoles and isoxazoles prepared were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity *in vitro*. Compound no. 11 was tested against *M. tuberculosis* (activity - 100 r/ml), no. 12 against *T. mentagrophytes*, no. 13 against *M. tuberculosis* (activity - 25 r/ml), no. 14 against *V. comma*, no. 15 against *K. leb* and *S. aureus*, no. 18 against *M. tuberculosis* (activity - 1.56 r/ml), no. 19 against *M. tuberculosis* and *T. mentagrophytes* and no. 20 against *E. coli*. and *C. albicans*.

TABLE I—M.P. AND YIELD OF THE COMPOUNDS* I-III

Sl. No.	Com-pound	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.	I	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	133	92.59
2.	I	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	Br	156	79.79
3.	I	CH ₃	Br	H	CH ₃	105	89.56
4.	I	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	154	86.35
5.	I	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	Br	97	83.00
6.	I	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	CH ₃	139	74.37
7.	I	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	Br	158	74.26
8.	I	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	Br	114	65.68
9.	I	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Br	H	CH ₃	115	59.51
10.	II	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	148	82.38
11.	II	CH ₃	Br	H	OH	130	65.58
12.	II	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	131	69.60
13.	II	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	OH	126	74.47
14.	II	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	Br	136	41.79
15.	III	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Br	182	78.57
16.	III	CH ₃	Br	H	OH	100	56.12
17.	III	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	Br	148	64.88
18.	III	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	Br	105	56.17
19.	III	C ₆ H ₅	Br	H	OH	141	50.84
20.	III	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	Br	122	48.37
21.	III	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Br	H	OH	167	42.16

* All new compounds analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N.

Two compounds, 1-phenyl-3, 5-dimethyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl benzeneazo) pyrazole and 1, 5-diphenyl-3-methyl-4-(4'-bromo-2'-methyl benzeneazo) pyrazole (No. 10 and 12) were also screened

for anti-inflammatory activity but no significant activity was observed.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Principal, St. John's College, Agra for necessary facilities. Thanks are also due to Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for anti-inflammatory activity tests.

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